

Studies on Colour and Constitution: Applications of Forster's Rule

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Relative acidities and basicities of a series of heterocyclic nuclei have been evaluated with the help of absorption maxima data of the following groups of compounds:

- (i) Dimethin merocyanines and their aza analogues.
- (ii) *p*-Dialkylaminobenzylidene derivatives of ketomethylene compounds and their aza analogues.
- (iii) *p*-Dialkylaminostyryl dyes and their aza analogues.
- (iv) Unsymmetrical cyanines and their aza analogues.

Brooker (*Rev. Mod. Phys.*, 1942, 14, 275) devised a method based on "deviation" for estimating the relative basicities and acidities of the various heterocyclic nuclei. In the present work, the relative basicities and acidities of a series of heterocyclic basic or acidic nuclei have been determined however, with the help of Forster's rule (*Z. Elektrochem.*, 1939, 45, 548). The method is based on absorption shift for replacement of =CH— by =N— in the chromophoric chain linking the heterocyclic nuclei concerned. Forster's rule states that the absorption maximum of a dye will increase with the decreasing tendency of the chain of atoms (chromophores) to take up the characteristic charge. The chromophoric atoms carry charges only in the excited state and the nature of the charge and their relative contributions largely depend on their energies.

Estimation of Relative Acidities

Determination of the relative acidities of a series of heterocyclic ketomethylene nuclei by this method has been accomplished by studying the absorption shift involved in the structural change from =CH— to =N— in dimethinmerocyanines (I: X=CH, N). The desired dimethin merocyanine (I: X=CH) was prepared by two methods, viz., (i) by condensing 5-ethoxymethylene-ketomethylene compound (formed by reaction of ethyl orthoformate and the keto methylene compound) with 4-phenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide and (ii) by condensing the ketomethylene compound with 2-(2-acetanilidovinyl)-4-phenylthiazole methiodide (Rout and Patnaik, this *Journal*, 1957, 34, 543). The corresponding aza analogue (I: X=N) was prepared by condensing the ethoxymethylene derivative with 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole methiodide.

In (I) the excited structure carrying X^- has greater significance than structures carrying X^+ because of the presence of one more double bond in the former than in the latter one. Therefore, for the replacement of $X=CH$ by $X=N$, the relative contribution of (Ib: $X=N$) to the resonance hybrid will be more than (Ib: $X=CH$) because of greater stability of $-N^-$ in comparison to $-CH_2^-$. Therefore, in accordance with Forster's rule, a hypsochromic shift is predicted for such structural change in (I).

As, in the above compounds, the hypsochromic shift is due to the increased significance of the excited structure, it follows that with increase in acidity (i.e., electron attracting property) of the nucleus A, the contribution of the excited structure (Ib) to the resonance hybrid would be diminished. In other words, in a series of dyes derived from weakly acidic nuclei and a fixed basic nucleus, as the acidity of the acidic nucleus is gradually increased, the amount of hypsochromic shift will gradually decrease. From examination of the data in Table I, it would appear therefore that the acidic nuclei may be arranged in order of decreasing acidity as follows: isoxazolone > pyrazolone > rhodanine.

TABLE I

Shift for replacement of $=CH-$ by $=N-$ in dimethin merocyanine.

Nature of nucleus A in (I).	Absorption maxima ($m\mu$).		Observed shift.
	X=CH.	X=N.	
3-Phenylrhodanine:	510	485	-25 $m\mu$
1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone	501	490	-11
3-Phenylisoxazolone	496	490	-6

N.B. Expected shift: Hypsochromic.

The relative acidities have also been evaluated from the shift in absorption maxima for replacement of $=CH-$ by $=N-$ in the *p*-dialkylaminobenzylidene derivatives of ketomethylene compounds (II: $X=CH$). The *p*-dialkylaminobenzylidene derivatives were obtained by condensing the ketomethylene compounds with *p*-dialkylaminobenzaldehyde. Their aza analogues (II: $X=N$) were obtained by using *p*-nitrosodialkylaniline in place of *p*-dialkylaminobenzaldehyde for condensation with ketomethylene compounds.

In such a case, by applying considerations as applied to the β -anilino vinyl derivatives and its aza analogue (Knott and Williams, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1951, 1586), the most likely excited structure involves $-X^+$ and not $-X^-$ as in (I). Consequently, for replacement of $=CH-$ by $=N-$, the characteristic charge would change from $-CH^+$ to $-N^+$ and because of the greater stability of $-CH^+$ in comparison to $-N^+$, the contribution of the interauxochromic, ionic excited structure to the resonance hybrid would increase or, in other words, Forster's rule predicts a bathochromic shift for replacement of $=CH-$ by $=N-$ in (II). This is actually

observed. The bathochromic shift in these dyes is mainly caused due to the decreased significance of the excited structure (IIb). The significance of the latter would increase with increase in acidity of the nucleus A. In other words, the bathochromic shift will gradually increase. The acidic nuclei constituting the dye in Table II may be arranged in the decreasing order of acidity as: isoxazolone > pyrazolone > rhodanine > thiohydantoin.

TABLE II
Shift for replacement of =CH— by =N— in *p*-dialkylaminobenzylidene derivatives of ketomethylene compound.

Nature of nucleus A in (II).	Absorption maxima.		Observed shift.
	X=CH.	X=N.	
3-Phenylisoxazolone	490 m μ	545 m μ	+55 m μ
1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone	470	520	+50
3-Phenylrhodanine	480	505	+25
3- <i>m</i> -Tolyl-3-thiohydantoin	450	470	+20

N.B. Expected shift: Bathochromic.

Estimation of Relative Basicities

The relative basicities (electron donating ability) of a series of heterocyclic nuclei can be assessed from the shift resulting from the structural change from =CH— to =N— in the *p*-dialkylaminostyryl dyes (III: X=CH) derived from such nuclei. The styryl dye (III: X=CH) was prepared by condensing the quaternary salt with *p*-dialkylaminobenzaldehyde. The corresponding aza analogue (III: X=N) was obtained by using *p*-nitrosodialkylaniline.

Here also, the most likely excited structure involves X^+ as in (II). Hence by applying the considerations made above, a bathochromic shift will be observed for such compounds (III) for a structural change from =CH— to =N—. The bathochromic shift will be gradually increased as the basicity of the nucleus, forming the dye, is decreased. From the results in Table III, the basic nuclei may therefore be arranged in order of decreasing basicity as: quinoline-2 > 4-*p*-bromophenylthiazole, 4-*p*-chlorophenylthiazole > 4-phenylthiazole > quinoline-2.

TABLE III
Shift for replacement of =CH— by =N— in *p*-dimethylaminostyryl dyes.

Nature of nucleus A (in III).	Absorption maxima.		Observed shift.
	X=CH.	X=N.	
Quinoline-2	527 m μ	590 m μ	+63 m μ
4-Phenylthiazole	490	540	+50
4- <i>p</i> -Bromophenylthiazole	490	530	+40
4- <i>p</i> -Chlorophenylthiazole	490	530	+40
Pyridine-2	459	490	+31

N.B. Expected shift: Bathochromic.

EXPERIMENTAL

5-(3'-Methyl-4'-phenylthiazolin-2'-ylidene-aminomethylene)-3-phenylrhodanine.—A mixture of 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole methiodide (1.6 g.) and of 5-ethoxymethylene-3-phenylrhodanine (1.35 g.) was boiled in absolute ethanol and triethylamine for 25 minutes. The product separated on cooling after removal of excess of the solvent. Recrystallisation from methanol gave lustrous golden needles, m.p. 300°, yield 54%. (Found: C, 58.37; H, 3.72. $C_{20}H_{15}ON_3S_3$ requires C, 58.53; H, 3.90%). The analytical data of the other aza analogues of merocarbocyanines are recorded in Table VA.

5-(p-Dimethylamino-anilino-methylene)-3-phenylrhodanine.—A mixture of 3-phenylrhodanine (1.05 g. and p-nitrosodimethylaniline (0.75 g.) was boiled in absolute ethanol in presence of piperidine (2 drops) for 40 minutes. Removal of the solvent at atmospheric pressure resulted in the separation of 1.3 g. of the product. Recrystallisation from ethanol gave red plates, m.p. 145°, yield 65%. (Found: C, 59.72; H, 4.33. $C_{17}H_{15}ON_3S_3$ requires C, 59.81; H, 4.41%). The analytical data of the other such compounds are shown in Table VB.

2-(p-Dimethylamino-anilino-methylene)-3-methyl-4-p-bromophenylthiazole Methiodide.—A mixture of 4-p-bromophenyl-2-methylthiazole methiodide (2.0 g.) and p-nitrosodimethylaniline (0.75 g.) was boiled in absolute ethanol in presence of piperidine (2 drops) for 30 minutes. The desired product (2 g.) separated out on cooling. Recrystallisation from ethanol furnished lustrous violet crystals, m.p. 193°, yield 55%. (Found: C, 43.18; H, 3.56. $C_{19}H_{19}N_3BrIS$ requires C, 43.00; H, 3.40%). The analytical data of the other such dyes are recorded in Table Vc.

TABLE V

Nature of nucleus A in (I).	M. P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
				Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
A. Aza analogues of dimethin merocyanines.							
3-Phenylisoxazolone	182-84°	52%	$C_{20}H_{15}O_2N_3S$	60.78	61.06	3.60	3.81
1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone	176-77°	56	$C_{21}H_{18}ON_4S$	67.12	67.37	4.64	4.81
B. Aza analogues of p-dimethylaminobenzylidene derivatives of ketomethylene compounds.							
3-Phenylisoxazolone	138°	70	$C_{17}H_{13}N_3O_2$	69.50	69.61	5.34	5.12
1-Phenyl-3-methylpyrazolone	147°	60	$C_{18}H_{18}ON_4$	70.43	70.60	5.64	5.88
3-m-Tolyl-2-thiohydantoin	249°	50	$C_{18}H_{18}ON_4S$	63.80	63.91	5.11	5.33
C. Aza analogues of p-demethylaminostyryl dyes.							
4-Phenylthiazole	209°	50	$C_{19}H_{20}N_3IS$	50.64	50.78	4.23	4.45
4-p-Chlorophenylthiazole	190°	55	$C_{19}H_{19}N_3SCHI$	47.03	47.17	3.48	3.81
Quinoline-2	195°	50	$C_{19}H_{20}N_3I$	54.53	54.68	4.62	4.80
Pyridine-2	178°	50	$C_{15}H_{18}N_3I$	48.83	49.05	4.90	5.05

(5-Methyl-2-benzothiazole)[(3-methyl-2-(4-phenylthiazole))-8 azamethin Cyanine Iodide.—A mixture of 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole methiodide (3.2 g.) and 2-methylmercaptobenzothiazole methiodide (3.2 g.) was boiled in absolute ethanol in presence of triethylamine for 10 minutes. The desired product separated on cooling. Recrystallisation from methanol yielded straw-yellow crystals, m.p. 246°, yield 55%. (Found: C, 46.45; H, 3.44. $C_{18}H_{18}N_3IS_2$ requires C, 46.32; H, 3.29%).

(1-Methyl-2-quinoline)[(3-methyl-2-(4-phenylthiazole))-10-azatrimethin Cyanine Iodide.—A mixture of 2-(2-acetanilidovinyl)-quinoline methiodide (1.32 g.) and 4-phenyl-2-aminothiazole methiodide (0.96 g.) was boiled in dry pyridine for 5 minutes. The desired product separated on addition of water. Two recrystallisations from ethanol gave red needles, m.p. 217-18°, yield 50%. (Found: C, 54.30; H, 4.01. $C_{22}H_{20}N_3IS$ requires C, 54.43; H, 4.12%).

(3-Methyl-2-benzothiazole) [3-methyl-2-(4-p-methoxyphenylthiazole)]-12-azapentamethin Cyanine Iodide.—A mixture of 2-(2-acetanilido-1, 3-butadienyl)-benzothiazole methiodide (2.3 g.) (Rout and Patnaik, this *Journal*, 1958, 25, 511) and 4-p-methoxyphenyl-2-aminothiazole methiodide (1.75 g.) was boiled in dry pyridine for 6 minutes. The product separated on addition of ether. Recrystallisation from ethanol gave violet needles, m.p. 135°, yield 60%. (Found: C, 50.23; H, 3.91. $C_{23}H_{22}ON_3IS_2$ requires C, 50.46; H, 4.02%).

(3-Methyl-2-benzothiazole) [3-methyl-2-(4-p-ethoxyphenylthiazole)]-14-azahexamethin Cyanine Iodide.—A mixture of 4-p-ethoxyphenyl-2-aminothiazole methiodide (1.09 g.) and 2-(acetanilido-1,3,5-hexatrienyl)-benzothiazole methiodide (1.47 g.) (Rout and Patnaik, *loc. cit.*) was boiled in absolute ethanol and triethylamine for 2 minutes. The desired product separated on chilling. Recrystallisation from ethanol gave green crystals, m. p. 212-13°, yield 45%. (Found: C, 53.02; H, 4.22. $C_{26}H_{26}ON_3IS_2$ requires C, 53.16; H, 4.43 %). The analytical data of other unsymmetrical azacyanines are shown in Table VI.

TABLE VI
Unsymmetrical azacyanines.

Nature of nucleus A in (IV).	Nature of nucleus B in (IV).	Value of n	M.P.	Yield.	Formula.	% Carbon.		% Hydrogen.	
						Found.	Calc.	Found.	Calc.
Quinoline-2	4-Phenylthiazole	0	247-48°	50%	$C_{20}H_{18}N_3IS$	52.20	52.79	3.81	3.93
Benzothiazole	,,	1	210-11°	50	$C_{20}H_{18}N_3IS_2$	48.64	48.87	3.50	3.66
,,	Benzothiazole	2	250-61°	40	$C_{22}H_{22}N_3IS_2$	50.70	50.86	4.10	4.24
,,	4-Phenylthiazole	2	160°	50	$C_{22}H_{20}N_3IS_2$	50.90	51.06	3.64	3.87
,,	4-p-Bromophenylthiazole	2	185-86°	60	$C_{22}H_{19}N_3BrIS_2$	44.16	44.30	3.03	3.19
,,	4-p-Ethoxyphenylthiazole	2	175-76°	50	$C_{24}H_{24}ON_3IS_2$	51.17	51.34	4.10	4.28
Quinoline-2	4-Phenylthiazole	2	195°	40	$C_{24}H_{22}N_3IS$	56.19	56.37	4.20	4.30
Benzothiazole	4-Phenylthiazole	3	175-76°	45	$C_{24}H_{22}N_3IS$	52.88	53.04	3.90	4.05
Quinoline-2	,,	3	210-12°	50	$C_{26}H_{24}N_3IS$	58.02	58.10	4.30	4.47

Funds received from Board of Scientific and Industrial Research, Orissa, India, in support of this investigation are gratefully acknowledged.